

EdPuzzle: Technology-based Assessment in Mathematics Education

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Abstract

Aims: This study examines the effectiveness of EdPuzzle as a technology-based assessment tool in mathematics education, specifically in enhancing students' comprehension of dividing rational expressions through interactive video lessons.

Study Design: A quasi-experimental research design was employed, comparing pre-test and post-test results to assess student improvement. The study encompassed both quantitative and qualitative approaches.

Place and Duration of Study: The study was conducted at the University of Eastern Philippines, Laoang Campus, Northern Samar, during the school year 2024-2025.

Methodology: The study targeted 18 third-year Bachelor of Secondary Education Mathematics students. A pre-test assessed initial knowledge, followed by an intervention using EdPuzzle's interactive video exercises. A post-test integrated within EdPuzzle measured progress. Quantitative data were analyzed using frequency

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counts, mean scores, and a t-test to determine statistical significance. Additionally, thematic analysis of interviews with six students who showed significant improvement provided qualitative insights.

Results: Findings indicate that EdPuzzle substantially improves students' understanding of dividing rational expressions, with post-test scores showing marked progress. Statistical analysis confirmed significant differences between pre-test and post-test results, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Thematic analysis highlighted challenges related to accessibility, error management, and engagement.

Conclusion: EdPuzzle significantly enhances students' understanding of dividing rational expressions, with post-test scores showing notable improvement. Statistical analysis confirms its effectiveness, but challenges in accessibility, error management, and engagement suggest the need for interactive and adaptive features. These findings highlight EdPuzzle's potential as an effective technology-based assessment tool in mathematics education, underscoring its role in facilitating interactive and engaging learning experiences.

Keywords: EdPuzzle; technology-based assessment; student engagement; mathematics education.

1 Introduction

Among the many concepts students encounter, dividing rational expressions often poses a significant challenge. A rational expression is a ratio of two polynomials, much like a fraction. Dividing these expressions requires understanding polynomial factoring and simplifying complex fractions. By mastering this topic, students not only develop computational proficiency but also gain deeper insights into the relationships between algebraic expressions. Such knowledge empowers them to tackle more advanced mathematical problems and apply these skills in real-world situations, enhancing their overall educational experience.

According to Sanchez and Falle (2022), students often struggle with misconceptions and procedural errors when simplifying rational algebraic expressions, which can lead to significant difficulties in dividing them. Cetin (2022) highlights that students face challenges in understanding the underlying concepts of rational inequalities, which are closely related to rational expressions. Tañola and Lomibao (2024) emphasize the importance of cognitive and metacognitive strategies in improving students' understanding and application of mathematical concepts, including dividing rational expressions. Famulagan and Paylangco (2024) discuss the trends in mathematics education research in the Philippines, noting that problem-solving and curriculum development are key areas of focus, which are essential for addressing the challenges students face in dividing rational expressions. According to Borja and Acorda (2023), rational expressions are considered foundational for higher-level mathematical concepts and real-world applications. Despite their significance, students often face challenges in grasping these concepts, which can impede their overall mathematical proficiency. These studies collectively highlight the need for targeted interventions and instructional strategies to help students overcome the difficulties associated with dividing rational expressions.

In recent years, the integration of technology into mathematics education has opened new avenues for assessing students' understanding and progress (Geraniou & Crisan, 2024). According to Hjelte, Schindler, and Nilsson (2021), technology-based assessments can help capture students' reasoning processes more effectively than traditional methods. Similarly, Ukobizaba, Nizeyimana, and Mukuka (2021) highlight the importance of assessment strategies in enhancing students' problem-solving skills, suggesting that technology can play a significant role in this area. Technology-based assessment in mathematics has become increasingly significant due to its potential to enhance the learning experience and improve educational outcomes. Alrababah & Molnár (2021) examine the evolution of technology-based assessment over the past three decades, highlighting its transformative impact on educational assessment. The integration of technology in assessment practices offers several advantages, including increased efficiency, precision, and engagement. According to Weigand et al. (2024) and Pala et al. (2025), technology has transformed teaching, learning, and assessment in mathematics education, highlighting the benefits of personalized and adaptive assessment systems. Weigand et al. (2024) discuss the increasing role of digital technology in mathematics education, transforming teaching, learning, and assessment. They highlight new research directions, including teachers' mathematical and digital competencies, teachers as designers of digital resources, and long-term initiatives to support innovative teaching practices. In addition, the study of Drijvers and Sinclair (2023) emphasizes how digital tools foster active participation and deeper engagement with mathematical concepts, leading to improved performance and confidence among learners. Moreover, the study of Cabugwason (2024) found that pre-service math teachers use various math apps to enhance their knowledge, but face challenges like limited internet access, confusing interfaces, and costs. It

recommends user-friendly designs, comprehensive instructions, and strategic integration of apps by educators to support diverse learning styles. Additionally, according to Nobis (2021), by increasing the availability of digital technologies, teachers could improve their digital usage, literacy, and teaching efficiency in mathematics.

The use of technology for formative assessments that provide ongoing feedback to students and teachers has not been sufficiently explored. Most existing studies focus on summative assessments that evaluate student learning at the end of a term or course, leaving a gap in understanding how technology can support continuous learning and improvement (Geraniou & Crisan, 2024). Additionally, there is a lack of comprehensive studies on teacher training and support for the effective implementation of technology-based assessments. Professional development programs are essential for helping teachers integrate these tools into their teaching practices, yet research on this aspect remains limited (Geraniou & Crisan, 2024).

Despite advancements in educational technology, many educators still rely on traditional assessment methods, which may not fully capture students' understanding and progress. According to Sinclair et. al. (2020), traditional assessment methods often leave gaps in learning, preventing students from addressing misconceptions promptly. The research highlights the importance of formative evaluation techniques that provide immediate feedback, enabling educators to adjust instruction and support students effectively. One such tool that has gained prominence in formative assessment is Edpuzzle, which allows educators to integrate interactive elements into video-based learning. Edpuzzle enables teachers to embed questions, voiceovers, and comments within videos, fostering active engagement and deeper comprehension. According to Asiri (2021), Edpuzzle provides instant feedback, helping students identify errors and refine their understanding in real time. Additionally, Alvarez-Alvarez & Mischel (2024) further highlight that Edpuzzle serves as a dynamic and motivating self-learning tool, making it an effective resource for both educators and students.

Given these challenges, it is therefore essential to explore innovative assessment tools like EdPuzzle, a platform that allows teachers to create interactive video lessons with embedded questions and feedback, addressing these challenges effectively. EdPuzzle provides instant feedback, enabling students to learn from their mistakes in real time. It allows for personalized learning experiences by tailoring feedback to individual students, ensuring they receive specific guidance based on their needs. Additionally, EdPuzzle's engaging content keeps students motivated and involved in the learning process. The platform also offers detailed analytics, giving teachers insights into student performance and areas that need improvement.

Similarly, Ernawati et al. (2023) found that the development of inquiry-based interactive Edpuzzle media led to a high level of effectiveness in improving students' learning outcomes in mathematics. Additionally, a study conducted by Janaki et al. (2022) examined the effectiveness of EdPuzzle in the learning process. The research found that EdPuzzle enhances student engagement and interaction, resulting in active learning.

Building on these findings, this study aimed to examine the effectiveness of Edpuzzle as a tool for assessing and enhancing students' understanding of mathematical concepts. Additionally, the study will examine the potential benefits of using Edpuzzle for both formative and summative assessments in mathematics education and explore students' experiences of utilizing Edpuzzle as an assessment tool in the classroom. This study can provide valuable insights into the role of technology-based assessments in improving mathematics education.

1.1 Research questions

This study examined the EdPuzzle as a technology-based assessment tool in Mathematics by comparing participants' pre-test and post-test results. It also explored their experiences using EdPuzzle, providing insights into its impact on student learning and assessment.

1. What do the pre-test and post-test results indicate about the participants?
2. To what extent would the feedback from the participants in the pre-test be different from their feedback in the post-test results?
3. How do participants perceive their experiences using EdPuzzle as a technology-based assessment tool in Mathematics?

2 Methodology

2.1 Research design

This study employs a quasi-experimental research design to examine the effectiveness of EdPuzzle as a technology-based assessment tool. Initially, a pre-test with multiple-choice questions will be administered in a controlled classroom setting to assess students' baseline knowledge and skills. Following the pre-test, students will engage with EdPuzzle videos that provide step-by-step explanations, practice problems, and interactive features. These videos allow for self-paced learning, ensuring active engagement through embedded assessment questions. The responses to these questions will serve as the post-test, measuring students' progress and mastery of dividing rational expressions. The study will compare pre-test and post-test results to determine the impact of EdPuzzle on student performance in dividing rational expressions. Statistical analysis will be conducted to assess the significance of any observed improvements. Additionally, interviews with a selected group of students will provide qualitative insights into their experiences, perceptions of EdPuzzle, and any challenges encountered. The findings will offer a comprehensive understanding of EdPuzzle's effectiveness as an assessment and learning tool.

2.2 Participants

The participants for this study were all 3rd-year students majoring in Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) Mathematics at the University of Eastern Philippines, Laoang Campus, who were officially enrolled during the academic year 2024-2025. Thus, a total of 18 participants were included in this study. Six participants were selected for the interview based on the criteria set by the researchers, wherein students whose post-test scores showed an improvement of at least two points compared to their pre-test results were chosen. These selected participants were asked to respond to questions provided by the researchers, offering insights into the factors that contributed to their score improvements.

2.3 Sampling methods

Purposive sampling of participants was employed in this study. The target population consisted of 3rd-year Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) Mathematics students. The selection criteria included students who were enrolled in the 3rd year of the BSED Mathematics program at the University of Eastern Philippines, Laoang Campus, and had their mobile phones. This specific group was selected because they possessed the requisite background knowledge for the study's focus on educational interventions and technology-based assessments in mathematics education. The purposive sampling approach ensured that the selected participants were highly relevant to the research questions and capable of providing valuable insights. For the interview sampling, the researchers established specific criteria based on post-test performance improvement. Six individuals whose post-test scores showed an increase of at least two points compared to their pre-test results were chosen for the interview. This approach ensured that the perspectives of students who demonstrated measurable progress were captured, providing valuable insights into the factors contributing to their improvement and the effectiveness of the intervention.

2.4 Research instruments

The participants answered the same problems in dividing rational expressions during the pre-test and post-test to evaluate their knowledge and skills in dividing rational expressions. The post-test assessment was conducted using the EdPuzzle platform, which also served as the intervention. The questionnaire was adapted from the EdPuzzle platform. These assessments provided quantitative data on the effectiveness of EdPuzzle by comparing scores before and after the intervention. Second, the researchers conducted structured interviews with the chosen six participants to gather in-depth qualitative data on their experiences using EdPuzzle. The interview questions were adapted from Askar et al. (2009).

2.5 Data collection

Before commencing the study, the researchers sought permission through a letter addressed to their research teachers and advisers. Upon receiving approval, an additional letter was submitted to the Department Chair to

facilitate the distribution of the questionnaire to the participants. At the beginning of the study, the researchers personally distributed the questionnaire to the participants to ensure the reliability of the results. Participants were given ample time to read and complete the questionnaire. After the pre-test, the researchers introduced Edpuzzle to the participants. Edpuzzle was an interactive video tool where embedded questions within the videos also served as the post-test. Participants engaged with the Edpuzzle content during a designated period, ensuring they had ample time to interact with the material and answer the embedded questions. Following the completion of the Edpuzzle activities, selected participants were invited for interviews. The interviews were scheduled at a convenient time for the participants and were conducted one-on-one using a voice recording device. Before the interview, participants were informed that their data would be kept confidential and used solely for research purposes, ensuring that their identities remained undisclosed and that their academic performance in math or other subjects would not be affected. Only those students who consented to participate were interviewed. Subsequently, the collected data from the pre-tests, Edpuzzle post-tests, and interviews were tallied, tabulated, and analyzed to derive meaningful insights and conclusions.

2.6 Data analysis

The data analysis for this study encompassed both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The primary focus was on quantitative analysis to assess the effectiveness of EdPuzzle. Frequency counts, percentages, and the mean were used to analyze pre-test and post-test scores, providing a detailed overview of the distribution of scores and changes over time. The scoring system categorized student performance as follows: 9-11 (excellent), 6-8 (fair), 3-5 (poor), and 0-2 (very poor). This classification provided a clear interpretation of student progress before and after using EdPuzzle. The paired samples t-test was employed to identify any significant differences in student scores before and after the intervention, further emphasizing the impact of EdPuzzle on student performance. For qualitative analysis, thematic analysis was employed to investigate students' experiences with EdPuzzle. The process started with data familiarization, where researchers reviewed the collected responses from student interviews. Key phrases or statements were coded and grouped into themes that reflected common patterns or trends. These themes were reviewed, refined, and clearly defined to ensure accuracy and coherence. The final themes were incorporated into the study's findings, supported by student responses, to provide a comprehensive perspective on the effectiveness of EdPuzzle in enhancing students' performance in dividing rational expressions.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Pre-test and post-test results of the participants

Table 1 presents the pre-test and post-test scores of the participants on dividing rational expressions. The pre-test result shows that the most frequent scores were between 3 to 5, obtained by 12 or 67% of participants, which are interpreted as poor. Following this, there were four (4) or 22% scored between 0 to 2, interpreted as very poor. Lastly, there were two (2) or 11% achieved scores between 6 to 8, interpreted as fair. The average score was approximately 3.667, which is interpreted as poor. These findings indicate that, before the intervention, the participants generally had a poor level of understanding of dividing rational expressions.

Table 1. Pre-test and post-test results of the participants

Pre-test				Post-test			
Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Interpretation	Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Interpretation
6-8	2	11%	Fair	9-11	4	22%	Excellent
3-5	12	67%	Poor	6-8	8	45%	Fair
0-2	4	22%	Very Poor	3-5	6	33%	Poor
Average:3.667			Poor	Average:6.765			Fair

While these findings align with previous studies, such as those by Sanchez (2022), Lee & Boyadzhiev (2020), and Pouta et al. (2020), which highlighted students' struggles with rational expressions and fractions, the current study contributes new insights by examining specific patterns in student errors and misconceptions. Unlike prior research that primarily focused on conceptual difficulties, this study identifies recurring procedural mistakes, particularly in fraction division rules, that impact. Moreover, the findings suggest that intervention strategies tailored to addressing these errors could be a key factor in improving student performance.

These results reinforce the urgent need for targeted instructional approaches to bridge foundational gaps and enhance students' comprehension of rational expressions. By pinpointing the precise areas of difficulty, this study offers a fresh perspective on how educators can refine teaching strategies to support student learning in algebra.

In the post-test result, it was found that there were eight (8) or 45% who got a score between 6 to 8, interpreted as fair. There were six (6) or 33% who got a score between 3 to 5, which is interpreted as poor. Lastly, there were four (4) or 22% who got a score between 9 to 11, interpreted as excellent. The average post-test score was 6.765, interpreted as fair. These results indicate that the participants gained improvement compared to the pre-test scores. This implies that the EdPuzzle technology-based assessment in mathematics effectively enhanced the participants' understanding of dividing rational expressions.

These findings underscore the positive impact of EdPuzzle technology-based assessments in mathematics, reinforcing the idea that digital tools enhance student comprehension. This study expands on prior research by Weigand et al. (2024), which found that interactive assessments improve retention and understanding. Additionally, Morata (2024) identified significant improvements in mathematical competencies among students using EdPuzzle's interactive lessons, with the experimental group outperforming those taught through traditional methods. Moreover, Drijvers and Sinclair (2023) emphasized that digital tools foster active participation, leading to deeper engagement and increased confidence in problem-solving.

By demonstrating clear improvements in student performance, this study provides further evidence of the effectiveness of technology-driven learning environments in strengthening mathematical understanding. The results suggest that integrating digital assessments into mathematics instruction can be a powerful strategy for addressing common learning difficulties in rational expressions.

3.2 Significant difference between the pre-test results and post-test results

Table 2 shows the test of the significant difference between the pre-test and post-test results of the participants. It was revealed that the t-value was -4.915 and a p-value of 0.000. With a level of significance set at 0.05, the decision was made to reject the null hypothesis. The negative t-value indicates that the post-test scores were substantially higher than the pre-test scores, reinforcing the effectiveness of the intervention. A p-value of 0.000 suggests that the observed improvement is not due to random chance but rather a direct result of the EdPuzzle technology-based assessment. This statistical evidence supports the claim that EdPuzzle allows students to engage with mathematical content at their own pace, fostering better comprehension and skill acquisition.

Table 2. Significant difference between the pre-test results and post-test results

	t - value	p - value	Level of Significance	Decision	Interpretation
Pre-test and Post-test results	-4.915	.000	0.05	Reject H_0	Significant

The findings are consistent with prior research on EdPuzzle's educational impact. Alvarez-Alvarez et al. (2024) found that EdPuzzle serves as an engaging and dynamic self-learning tool, enabling students to absorb lessons through interactive video materials while receiving instant feedback to correct misunderstandings. Janaki et al. (2022) further demonstrated that students who utilized EdPuzzle exhibited higher engagement and interaction, leading to deeper learning outcomes compared to traditional instructional methods. Moreover, the study by Drijvers and Sinclair (2023) highlights that digital tools enhance student motivation and confidence, creating a more interactive and student-centered learning experience. These studies collectively support the conclusion that technology-driven assessments not only improve academic performance but also empower students to learn effectively at their own pace.

The statistical significance found in this study suggests that EdPuzzle is a valuable digital assessment tool that can bridge learning gaps, particularly in mathematical concepts like rational expressions. By integrating EdPuzzle into classroom instruction, educators can tailor learning experiences to individual student needs, enhance engagement, and drive meaningful improvements in mathematical competency.

3.3 Experiences of the participants in using edpuzzle as technology-based assessment in mathematics

A thematic analysis of interview transcripts revealed four major themes regarding participants' experiences: accessibility challenges, error management, user experience and engagement, and understanding of materials. These themes provide insight into the various factors influencing students' interaction with EdPuzzle.

3.4 Accessibility challenges

Participants encountered various challenges when first accessing EdPuzzle, particularly login difficulties and slow internet connectivity, which significantly disrupted their engagement with the platform. Unlike previous studies that primarily focused on general technological barriers, this study identifies specific struggles related to authentication errors, repeated login attempts, and buffering issues caused by weak connections. These findings emphasize that while EdPuzzle is an effective learning tool, its accessibility is influenced by digital infrastructure and user experience factors.

Although prior research has documented technological limitations in online learning such as Jose et al. (2023), who explored connectivity issues affecting student engagement, and Rizwan Rki (2025), who highlighted browser compatibility problems this study reveals that students faced unexpected obstacles unique to EdPuzzle's interface, such as repeated login failures that delayed lesson access. Fabito (2020) also addressed internet reliability issues in online education, but this study extends these observations by demonstrating how interruptions in video-based learning impact comprehension, requiring students to restart or repeat tasks multiple times due to unstable connections.

Here are some examples of responses that reflect this theme:

"The first issue was accessibility. The first time they required us to use Edpuzzle, we had a hard time accessing it, particularly with how to sign in or log in to our accounts on the platform. We had to sign in repeatedly, and only after several attempts were we finally able to access it."

"Another issue was the slow internet connection. Because of the weak signal, we kept having to go back and repeat the process of watching the video and answering the questions."

"Somewhat, it is not easy for me to use this kind of app or educational apps because, at first, the login process is a hassle sometimes due to the internet connection."

"Since it's my first time using Edpuzzle, I found it a bit challenging, especially because I struggled with logging into the platform."

Beyond inconvenience, these challenges disrupted the learning experience, causing delays, frustration, and reduced engagement. As noted in EdPuzzle's troubleshooting guide, login errors and buffering issues require intervention through technical support, yet this study suggests that educational institutions should proactively address digital accessibility concerns to improve technology-driven assessments.

By uncovering these new challenges and their direct impact on student learning, this study contributes to the broader discussion on integrating educational technology effectively. These findings reinforce the need for improved digital infrastructure, optimized platform usability, and institutional support to ensure that EdPuzzle and similar tools function seamlessly in diverse learning environments.

3.5 Error management

Participants reflected on the errors they encountered while using EdPuzzle, noting both the types of mistakes and their recoverability. While errors were common, they were generally minor and easily rectified, allowing students to continue engaging with the platform without significant disruption. These reflections align with findings from Macagba (2023), who explored how EdPuzzle enhances student interaction. The study highlights instances where students encounter minor technological errors but notes that these do not significantly disrupt

learning. EdPuzzle's user-friendly design allows students to quickly identify and correct mistakes, reinforcing its effectiveness as an educational tool.

Here are some examples of responses that reflect this theme:

"I made a few mistakes—as I remember, I got item numbers 9 and 11 wrong, and then usually just small ones like clicking the wrong button. But they're easy to fix and recover from without much frustration."

"I sometimes make errors, such as submitting incomplete answers. Although these mistakes aren't extremely severe, they can still affect the accuracy of my responses."

"Recovering from these mistakes wasn't always easy, especially since I wasn't familiar with how to fix them."

Additionally, Muhammad Dzulfikar Praseno (2021) examined EdPuzzle's resilience despite occasional technical issues. Students reported encountering minor errors such as login difficulties, video buffering, and question display glitches. However, they quickly adapted by refreshing pages, adjusting browser settings, or seeking instructor guidance (Praseno, 2021). Similarly, Azlan (2020) explored the broader e-learning landscape and noted that while minor technical errors occurred across different platforms, students were generally able to resolve them without significant disruption. These studies support the finding that while errors in EdPuzzle are common, they are generally minor and easily resolved (Adoro et al., 2024). The troubleshooting guide provided by EdPuzzle emphasizes simple solutions such as clearing browser cache, refreshing pages, and ensuring stable internet connections to mitigate common issues (EdPuzzle Support, 2025). This aligns with participants' reflections, affirming that EdPuzzle's error management is consistent with common digital learning experiences.

3.6 User experience and engagement

Participants had varying experiences with EdPuzzle—while many found its interactive features engaging and effective for learning, others struggled with technical issues that hindered their ability to fully benefit from the platform. These findings align with the study of Macagba (2020), which investigates how EdPuzzle influences student participation in online discussions. The study found that while EdPuzzle increases engagement, it does not necessarily improve the quality of student responses in synchronous sessions. Similarly, Su and Chiu (2020) examined how students perceive interactive learning tools like EdPuzzle, revealing that while many students appreciated the engaging aspects of the platform, their overall experience varied depending on personal preferences and technical limitations.

Here are some examples of responses that reflect this theme:

"Edpuzzle is a really good platform to use, especially when integrating it into asynchronous learning. It's effective because teachers can embed video tutorials that include discussions on how to solve specific problems or explain particular concepts in mathematics."

"After you answer a question, whether your answer is correct or not, the platform shows and explains the correct answer to that specific problem. This helps students understand the topic better and learn from their mistakes, making their knowledge more refined."

"My experience with Edpuzzle wasn't pleasant at first. The main reason was that I wasn't familiar with the app, and secondly, the poor internet connection made it a frustrating experience for me."

"It's pleasant to use—the interactive features make learning more engaging, though sometimes navigation can feel a bit clunky."

Additionally, Capilla et al. (2022) explored students' perceptions of digital tools used in online teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study found that while students appreciated the use of videos and interactive tools like EdPuzzle in the flipped classroom model, there were varying levels of satisfaction. Some students reported positive experiences, indicating that these tools enhanced their learning, while others faced challenges related to internet connectivity and the adaptability of the tools to their learning styles. Furthermore, Lupas et al. (2024)

and Notarte et al. (2024) emphasized the importance of considering individual student needs and technological access when implementing digital learning platforms. These mixed experiences underscore the necessity of refining EdPuzzle's usability and accessibility to ensure a more seamless learning experience for all students.

3.7 Understanding of materials

Participants reported that the structured and formative nature of EdPuzzle contributed positively to their understanding of the materials presented. The immediate feedback provided by the platform helped solidify their comprehension and allowed them to refine their learning process. These findings align with the study of Alvarez-Alvarez (2024), which found that students prefer visual and graphic materials to supplement their learning. This preference aligns with EdPuzzle's structured format, which helps students better comprehend the content and reinforces their understanding through interactive elements.

Here are some examples of responses that reflect this theme:

"It provides clear and structured discussions, along with a step-by-step process for solving problems, such as those involving mixed fractions. This made it easier for me to understand the topic."

"One of the most helpful aspects of Edpuzzle is its formative nature. After answering each question, whether I got it right or wrong, the platform explains the correct answer. This immediate feedback helps solidify my understanding and allows me to learn from my mistakes."

"Eventually, it became easier for me to understand the problem since I could go back, rewatch, and refresh my understanding. I could also return to the part I didn't understand."

Furthermore, Asiri (2021) highlights the role of immediate feedback in learning. By instantly showing students whether their responses are correct, EdPuzzle enables learners to solidify their comprehension on the spot, further supporting the notion that immediate feedback enhances understanding. Similarly, Baker (2019) explored how EdPuzzle enhances formative assessment in flipped classrooms. The research highlights that real-time feedback from multiple-choice questions and teacher comments helps students assess their understanding and refine their learning process effectively. Additionally, Balanquit et al. (2025) examined difficulties in assessing conceptual knowledge and error analysis, noting that while EdPuzzle aids comprehension, some students still struggle with deeper conceptual understanding. While edpuzzle proves to be a valuable tool in reinforcing learning, its effectiveness may be enhanced further with supplementary instructional support (Nobis, 2025), particularly for more complex topics that require deeper understanding.

4 Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate that, before the intervention, students had a limited understanding of dividing rational expressions. This highlights the necessity of targeted instructional approaches to bridge foundational gaps and enhance comprehension. The use of EdPuzzle as a technology-based assessment tool proved to be effective in improving student performance, reinforcing the benefits of digital learning environments in strengthening mathematical understanding.

Moreover, statistical evidence supports the claim that EdPuzzle allows students to engage with mathematical content at their own pace, fostering better comprehension and skill acquisition. The observed improvements suggest that integrating digital assessments into mathematics instruction can help address common learning difficulties, particularly in dividing rational expressions.

Given the statistical significance observed in this study, EdPuzzle can serve as a valuable tool for enhancing mathematics education beyond the specific context of rational expressions. Its adaptability allows for personalized learning experiences, making it suitable for a wide range of subjects and learning environments. Educators can leverage their features to provide timely feedback, facilitate self-paced learning, and address individual student needs effectively.

Furthermore, the challenges identified in this study underscore the need for institutional support in digital accessibility. Schools and universities should proactively improve technological infrastructure and provide

necessary training for educators and students to maximize the benefits of technology-driven assessments. Future research should explore how EdPuzzle can be optimized for diverse educational settings, ensuring that digital learning platforms remain inclusive and effective across different student populations.

This study contributes to the broader discussion on integrating educational technology effectively, offering valuable insights into the role of digital assessments in modern learning environments.

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence)

This research utilized ChatGPT, Cici, and Copilot—advanced AI language models—for paraphrasing paragraphs and checking grammatical errors. The free ChatGPT app, along with Cici and Copilot, was employed as a tool to enhance the clarity and readability of the text, ensuring that ideas were effectively communicated while maintaining the original meaning. The use of these AI models contributed to refining the language and structure of the manuscript.

Details of the AI usage are given below:

1. Used ChatGPT, Cici, and Copilot for paraphrasing paragraphs to improve the clarity and readability of the text.
2. Used ChatGPT, Cici, and Copilot for checking language and grammar to enhance overall accuracy and fluency.

Consent and Ethical Approval

This study emphasized ethical considerations to ensure fairness, accuracy, and reliability throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were thoroughly informed about the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time without facing any consequences. Interviews were conducted with participant consent, and responses were transcribed verbatim to ensure accuracy. Strict adherence to ethical principles, including informed consent, anonymity, and confidentiality, was maintained. Any potential biases were addressed to ensure an impartial and objective study. Furthermore, the research complied with ethical guidelines set by educational and research institutions to protect the rights and well-being of all participants.

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Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

References

Adoro, J. B., Dulay, E., Talenjale, M., Balanquit, C., & Nobis, M. (2024). Investigating the Influence of Attitude, Prior Knowledge, and Critical Thinking on Solving Algebraic Equations. *Formosa Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(6), 1993–2004. <https://doi.org/10.55927/fjmr.v3i6.9340>

- Alvarez-Alvarez, C., & Mischel, E. (2024). Edpuzzle for E-learning: A Study of Perceived Advantages and Limitations. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology (IJEDICT)*, 2024, Vol. 20, Issue 1, pp. 134-145. EJ1426560.pdf
- Asiri, A. (2021). EdPuzzle: a formative assessment tool. In *WAESOL Educator* (Vols. 46–46, Issue 2). 12.-Asiri-A.-2021.-Edpuzzle-A-formative-assessment-tool.-WAESOL-Educator-462-34-35.pdf
- Askar, P., Dönmez, O., Kizilkaya, G., Çevik, V., & Gültekin, K. (2009). Dimensions of Student Satisfaction on Online Programs. In *Encyclopedia of Distance Learning*. IGI Global, 585–590. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-60566-198-8.ch091>
- Asri, T. M., et. al. (2020). Investigating the use of internet applications for teaching at a higher educational level in the Indonesian context. *Arab World English Journal*, 11(2), 37–48. <https://doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol11no2.3>
- Azlan, C.A., et al., (2020), Teaching and learning of postgraduate medical physics using Internet-based e-learning during the COVID-19 pandemic – A case study from Malaysia, *Physica Medica* 80, 10–16. <https://doi.org/10.4102/hsag.v28i0.2427>
- Baker, K. (2019). Digital Assessment Techniques with Edpuzzle - Flipped Learning Network Hub. *Flipped Learning Network Hub*. <https://flippedlearning.org/syndicated/digital-assessment-techniques-with-edpuzzle/>
- Balanquit, C. & Nobis, M. (2025). Assessment of Conceptual Knowledge and Error Analysis in Mathematics among Pre-service Teachers. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Education and Society*. 7. 217-229. 10.55057/ijares 2025.7.1.20.
- Cabugwason, M. R., et. al. (2024). Math Apps in Math Education: Experiences and Challenges of Pre-Service Teachers. *IGNATIAN: International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(5), 1909–1922. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11235604>
- Capilla P., et al. (2022). Students' perception of digital tools used with online teaching methodologies in a pandemic context: a case study in Northern Chile. *Journal of Technology and Science Education*, 12(3), 596-610. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3926/jotse.1692>
- Cetin, O. F. (2022). The awareness of difficulties in solving rational inequality and a solution proposal. *Pedagogical Research*, 7(4), em0137. <https://doi.org/10.29333/pr/12392>
- Drijvers, P., & Sinclair, N. (2023). The role of digital technologies in mathematics education: purposes and perspectives. *ZDM*, 56(2), 239–248. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-023-01535-x>
- Ernawati, E., et. al. (2023). Developing of Inquiry-Based interactive EdPuzzle media to improve students' mathematics learning outcomes. *Jurnal Teknologi Pendidikan Jurnal Penelitian Dan Pengembangan Pembelajaran*, 8(2), 511. <https://doi.org/10.33394/jtp.v8i2.7971>
- Fabito, B. S., et. al (2020). Barriers and Challenges of Computing Students in an Online Learning Environment: Insights from One Private University in the Philippines. *International Journal of Computing Sciences Research*, [S.l.], v. 5, p. 441-458, sep. 2020. ISSN 2546-115X. <https://www.stepacademic.net/ijcsr/article/view/179>
- Famulagan, J. E., & Paylangco, C. L. (2024). Mathematics Education Research Trends in the Philippines: A Bibliometric Analysis using Scopus Database. *Pedagogy Review*, 3(1), 114–127. <https://doi.org/10.62718/vmca.pr-ijetas.3.1.sc-0524-004>
- Feng, M., et. al. (2023). Technology-Based support shows promising Long-Term impact on math learning: Initial results from a randomized controlled trial in middle schools. *WestEd*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED630781.pdf>

- Iannone, P., Moons, F., Druke-Noe, C., Geraniou, E., & Morselli, F. (2024). Assessment of students' learning mathematics with technology using video-based activities in an online course - UCL Discovery. <https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/10196604/>
- Janaki, B., & Surendran, K. R. (2022). Effectiveness of Using EdPuzzle – A Study in Velammal College of Engineering & Technology. *Journal of Hunan University Natural Sciences*, 49(12), 171–178. <https://doi.org/10.55463/issn.1674-2974.49.12.17>
- Jose, J. P., et. al. (2023). Struggle is Real: The experiences and challenges faced by Filipino tertiary students on lack of amidst the online learning. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 7, 174–181. https://scimatic.org/show_manuscript/1028
- Lee, H., & Boyadzhiev, I. (2020). Underprepared College Students' Understanding of and Misconceptions with Fractions. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 15(3). <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/7835>
- Lupas, L. B., Olchondra, J. A. A., Irinco, J. P. L., & Nobis Jr, M. L. Cracking the Math Code: Challenges and Strategies for Success Among Future Math Educators. [https://etcor.org/storage/iJOINED/Vol.%20III\(3\),%20158-168.pdf](https://etcor.org/storage/iJOINED/Vol.%20III(3),%20158-168.pdf)
- Macagba, Junefel C. et al. Unlocking Engagement: The Role of Edpuzzle in Augmenting Participation and Enhancing Responses During Contemporary Issues Discussions. *Sdssu Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, [S.I.], v. 8, p. 13-18, nov. 2023. ISSN 2408-3577. <https://smrj.nemsu.edu.ph/index.php/SMRJ/article/view/245>
- Miriam B. Borja, Pilar B. Acorda (2023). Enhancing Mathematical Skills on Rational Algebraic Expressions through Contextualized Activity Sheets cum Video. (2023). *International Journal of Arts and Social Science*, 6(11), 237–238. <https://www.ijassjournal.com/2023/V6I11/4146663743.pdf>
- Morata, J. A. (2024). Interactive Video-Based Learning on Least Learned Competencies in Mathematics of Grade 8 Students using EdPuzzle: A Basis for an Online Intervention. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14208188>
- Nobis Jr, M. L., Cui, A. P., Delmonte, C. M., De Guzman, B. C., Evardone, J. G., Caparoso, C. L., ... & Acebron, A. E. B. Symptoms, Determinants and Coping Strategies: A Qualitative Study of Test Anxiety among Pre-service Teachers. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2025/v5i51943>.
- Nobis, Jr., Martin, Factors Encouraging and Barriers to ICT Integration In Mathematics Teaching (January 06, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5243902> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5243902>
- Nobis, M. L. Jr. (2021). Digital literacy of mathematics teachers in state Universities and Colleges (SUCs). **Asian Journal of Research in Education and Social Sciences*, 3* (2), 99-113 <https://doi.org/10.1234/ajress.2021.03.02.99>
- Notarte, M., Aguilando, L. R., Larazi, N., Nobis, M., Acebron, A. (2024). Beyond Memorization: Building Problem-Solving Skills in Sequences for Future Math Teachers. *East Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*. 3. 10.55927/eajmr.v3i9.9437.
- Pala, C. A., Lagrimas, D., & Jr., M. L. N. (2025). Exploration of Chatbots in Mathematics Education for Innovative Learning Process. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports*, 19(5), 178-194. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajarr/2025/v19i51010>
- Pouta, M., Lehtinen, E. & Palonen, T. (2021). Student Teachers' and Experienced Teachers' Professional Vision of Students' Understanding of the Rational Number Concept. *Educ Psychol Rev* 33, 109–128 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-020-09536-y>

- Praseno, M. D. (2021). Improving Students' Writing Participation and Achievement in an Edpuzzle-Assisted Flipped Classroom. <https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.educafl.2021.004.01.01>
- Sanchez, L. C., & Falle, T. A. (2022). Difficulties Encountered by Junior High School on the Simplification of Rational Algebraic Expressions in Zambales, Philippines. *United International Journal for Research & Technology (UIJRT)*, 3(11), pp.39-45. [UIJRTV3I110006.pdf](https://doi.org/10.1177/00224669198784703)
- Sinclair, A. C., et. al. (2019). A review of the Evidence for Real-Time Performance Feedback to improve instructional practice. *The Journal of Special Education*, 54(2), 90–100. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00224669198784703>
- Su, C. Y., & Chiu, C. H. (2021). Perceived Enjoyment and Attractiveness Influence Taiwanese Elementary School Students' Intention to Use Interactive Video Learning. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 37(6), 574-583. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2020.1841423>
- Tañola, M. D., & Lomibao, L. S. (2024). Understanding How Students Learn Mathematics: A Systematic Literature Review of Contemporary Learning Strategies in Mathematics Education Post-2020. *Copyright © 2024 Science and Education Publishing. All Rights Reserved.* <https://doi.org/10.12691/jitl-4-1-11>
- Weigand, H., Trgalova, J., & Tabach, M. (2024d). Mathematics teaching, learning, and assessment in the digital age. *ZDM*, 56(4), 525–541. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-024-01612-9>

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